

TENSILE FAILURE OF BRITTLE-MATRIX FIBER COMPOSITES

D.B. Marshall

Rockwell International Science Center
Thousand Oaks, CA 91360
USA

A.G. Evans

Department of Materials Science
University of California
Berkeley, CA 94720
USA

Abstract

The tensile failure of a brittle matrix fiber composite has been analyzed as a function of fiber strength. Strong fibers remain intact during matrix fracture, resulting in multiple matrix cracks and a post-cracking load sustaining capability. Reduced fiber strength causes fiber failure in the crack wake and catastrophic failure from a single matrix crack. Strength and fracture resistance relations are derived for both fracture mechanisms, and microstructural trends elucidated. Furthermore, the transition between mechanisms is used as the basis for a failure map.

Introduction

Several tensile failure mechanisms have been observed in brittle materials reinforced by high strength brittle fibers (1-6). If the fibers have sufficient strength to remain intact after a crack extends completely through the matrix, the formation of multiple, regularly spaced matrix cracks precedes failure of the composite. In such materials the tensile strength of the composite can substantially exceed the stress for matrix cracking and large strains-to-failure can be achieved. On the other hand, if the fibers have lower strength, fiber failure may accompany matrix cracking. In this case failure of the composite coincides with failure of the matrix.

The applied stress required to cause matrix cracking according to either of these failure mechanisms can be considerably increased by the presence of the fibers. This reinforcement arises because separation of the crack surfaces involves some sliding of the matrix over the fibers. In general, this process requires debonding at the fiber/matrix interface followed by sliding against frictional forces. However, successfully reinforced ceramic-matrix composites exhibit no chemical bond between the fibers and matrix (4). The present paper is concerned with such unbonded

composites, in which the sliding of the matrix over the fibers is resisted only by frictional forces.

An analysis of the first matrix crack formation in composites that exhibit multiple cracking was developed recently (7). The crack growth was evaluated using a stress intensity approach in which the reinforcing effect of the fibers (i.e., the frictional forces) was represented as closure tractions applied to the crack surfaces. In the present paper, the stress intensity analysis is generalized to include the failure mechanism in which fiber failure occurs behind the crack tip. From this analysis it is possible to generate a failure map which defines transitions in failure mechanism as well as strength relations for each mechanism.

Fracture Mechanics Analysis

Formulation of Problem

Following the previous analysis (7), the matrix crack is formed in two hypothetical steps. First, all of the bonds across the prospective crack plane (in the fibers as well as the matrix) are cut and stress σ_∞ is applied (Figure 1a), causing the crack to open. In the second step tractions, T, are applied to the end of each fiber that lies within a distance d of the crack tip. The magnitude of T is chosen such that the fiber ends displace relative to the matrix and allow the fibers to be rejoined (Figure 1b). In a continuum approximation ($c \gg$ fiber spacing), this procedure is equivalent to applying a distribution of closing pressure $p(x)$ to the crack surfaces:

$$p(x) = \begin{cases} T(x) f & (x > c-d) \\ 0 & (x < c-d) \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where x represents the position on the crack surface (Figure 1b) and f is the volume fraction of fibers. The closure induced by the pressure $p(x)$ opposes the opening due to the applied stress σ_∞ . The influence of the applied stress on the crack tip stress intensity can be exactly evaluated by regarding the stresses as a uniform opening pressure, σ_∞ , acting along the crack surfaces. Therefore, with the crack surfaces being subject to net pressure ($\sigma_\infty - p(x)$), a composite stress intensity factor for a penny crack* embedded in an infinite medium can be defined as;

$$K = 2(c/\pi)^{1/2} \int_0^1 \frac{[\sigma_\infty - p(X)]X dX}{\sqrt{1-X^2}} \quad (2)$$

where $X = x/c$.

The stress intensity K characterizes the composite stress and strain fields in the region immediately ahead of the matrix crack. In this region, the matrix and fiber strains must be compatible, whereupon the stresses exhibit the composite relationship

* In the previous analysis for multiple matrix cracking, penny cracks and straight cracks yielded almost identical results. Therefore, for convenience, only penny cracks are considered explicitly in this paper.

$$\sigma_m / E_m = \sigma_\infty / E \quad (3a)$$

where σ_m is the matrix stress and E is the composite modulus,

$$E = E_m(1-f) + E_f f$$

with E_m and E_f referring to the Young's modulus of the matrix and fibers, respectively. The matrix and composite stress intensities scale with the stresses, such that

$$K = K_m E / E_m \quad (3b)$$

where K_m is the stress intensity factor in the matrix. The condition for equilibrium crack growth (in the absence of environmental effects) is given by setting K_m equal to the critical stress intensity factor, K_c , for the matrix. Therefore, the criterion for crack growth can be expressed in terms of K as;

$$K = K_c \equiv K_o E / E_m \quad (4)$$

Thus, Eqs. (2) and (4) relate the matrix cracking condition to the applied stress σ_∞ .

Evaluation of K in Eq. (2) requires a separate calculation of the pressure distribution $p(x)$. Analysis of fiber pullout from the matrix reveals that the closure pressure is related to the crack opening, u , at a given location by

$$p = 2[u\tau f^2 E_f (1 + \eta) / R]^{1/2} \quad (5)$$

where $\eta = E_f f / E_m (1-f)$, R is the fiber radius, and τ is the sliding frictional stress at the interface. However, the crack opening at a given position is determined by the entire distribution of surface tractions. For a penny crack (7),

$$u(x) = \frac{4(1-\nu^2)_c}{\pi E} \int_x^1 \frac{1}{\sqrt{s^2 - x^2}} \int_0^s \frac{[\sigma_\infty - p(t)] t dt}{\sqrt{s^2 - t^2}} ds \quad (6)$$

where s and t are normalized position coordinates and ν is the Poisson's ratio of the composite. Therefore, analysis of matrix cracking by the stress intensity approach requires solution of Eqs. (5) and (6) to obtain the crack surface tractions, followed by evaluation of the integral in Eq. (2) and combination with the crack growth criterion, Eq. (4).

Figure 1 - Hypothetical operations used to evaluate the closure effect of fibers bridging a matrix crack.

Calculation of Closure Effect of Fibers: Analytical Approximation

Rigorous analytical solutions for $u(x)$ cannot be obtained from Eqs. (5) and (6). Therefore, an approximate form for the crack profile is assumed, by taking the solution from Eq. (6) for a crack subject to uniform pressure, with the magnitude of the opening governed by the net stress intensity factor K (Eq. 2);

$$u(x) = 2(1 - \nu^2)K c^{1/2}(1 - x^2/c^2)^{1/2}/E \pi^{1/2} \quad (7)$$

This approximate solution for the crack opening gave results closely comparable to numerical computations when applied to steady-state matrix cracking (7). The actual pressure distribution is obtained by combining Eqs. (5) and (7) to give

$$p(x) = [\alpha K c^{1/2}(1 - x^2/c^2)^{1/2}]^{1/2} \quad (x < c - d) \quad (8a)$$

where

$$\alpha = 8(1 - \nu^2)\tau f^2 E_f(1 + \eta)/E R \pi^{1/2} \quad (8b)$$

With this pressure distribution, the net stress intensity factor (Eq. (2)) is given by

$$K = K_\infty - K_p \quad (9a)$$

where

$$K_\infty = \Omega \sigma_\infty c^{1/2} \quad (9b)$$

$$K_p = (16\alpha/9\pi)^{1/2} K^{1/2} d^{3/4} (2 - d/c)^{3/4} \quad (9c)$$

and $\Omega = 2/\sqrt{\pi}$. The terms K_∞ and K_p represent the contributions to the crack tip stress intensity due to the applied load and the fiber closure tractions, respectively.

Multiple Matrix Cracking: No Fiber Failure

If all of the fibers that intersect the crack plane remain intact the traction-induced stress intensity (Eq. (9c)) becomes

$$K_p = (16\alpha/9\pi)^{1/2} K^{1/2} c^{3/4} \quad (10)$$

Thus, the closure effect of the fibers increases indefinitely with crack length. The mechanics of crack growth is most conveniently investigated by combining Eqs. (9) and (10), setting $K = K_c$, and solving for σ_∞ to obtain an equilibrium-stress/crack-size function;

$$\sigma_c = K_c / \Omega c^{1/2} + [16\alpha K_c / 9\pi \Omega^2]^{1/2} c^{1/4} \quad (11)$$

This function can be conveniently expressed in normalized form,

$$\sigma_c / \sigma_m = (1/3)(c/c_m)^{-1/2} + (2/3)(c/c_m)^{1/4} \quad (c \leq c_o) \quad , \quad (12)$$

where

$$c_m = (9\pi K_c / 4\alpha)^{2/3} \quad (13a)$$

and

$$\sigma_m = (3/\Omega)(4\alpha K_c / 9\pi)^{2/3} \quad (13b)$$

Equation (12) provides a relation between normalized stress and crack length parameters, σ_c/σ_m and c/c_m , without explicit reference to material and microstructural properties (these properties enter only in their influence on the normalizing factors c_m and σ_m). Thus, the mechanics of crack growth may be examined independently of the specific composite system.

It is necessary to distinguish between large and small cracks in this system. Large cracks must experience a crack opening which asymptotically approaches (but cannot exceed) the equilibrium separation of the completely failed matrix (i.e., two half planes connected by fibers). However, the crack opening expressed by Eq. (7) is unbounded at large c . Therefore, the preceding analysis is used only for cracks smaller than a transition crack length, c_0 , defined by setting $p = \sigma_\infty$ at $X = 0$ in Eq. (8a):

$$c_0 = (\sigma_\infty^2 / \alpha K_c)^{2/3} \quad (14)$$

For larger cracks, the net force in the fibers that bridge the crack over the area where the asymptotic opening is approached (i.e., $X < c - c_0$) must balance the applied load. In this case, the crack-tip stress concentration is induced exclusively over the length c_0 and the stress required to extend the crack must be independent of the total crack length. The steady-state stress, given by (Eq. (11) with $c = c_0$) is equal to σ_m .

The complete equilibrium-stress/crack-size function is plotted in Figure 2. Also plotted for comparison is a solution obtained by numerical integration. The two solutions show similar trends. At small crack lengths, the solutions converge, but at large crack lengths the numerical steady-state stress is ~ 20% lower than the approximate analytical value. It is noted that the stress required to propagate a matrix crack is almost independent of crack length for cracks larger than $c_m/3$. This defines the range of crack sizes over which steady-state conditions apply. The crack response in this region contrasts with the behavior of cracks in unreinforced brittle materials, for which the strength decreases with $c^{-1/2}$.

Broken Fibers Behind Crack Tip

When fibers fail behind the crack tip, rigorous analysis of K_p would involve consideration of the statistical nature of fiber strengths, combined with knowledge of the stress distributions over the fibers. However, in order to allow analytical progress in the present analysis, a single-valued fiber strength, S , is assumed.* Then the position within the crack at which

* A single-valued fiber strength implies that fiber failure occurs between the crack surfaces, so that broken fibers do not exert closure forces on the crack. On the other hand, a statistical distribution of fiber strengths would allow fiber failure within the matrix and continued closure effect until the broken fiber pulls out of the matrix. Therefore, the present calculations yield lower bound values of composite strengths.

Figure 2 - Equilibrium-stress/crack-size functions for penny-shaped matrix cracks in a composite containing high strength fibers and in a monolithic material.

fiber failure occurs is defined by Eq. (8a), with $p(x) = Sf$ at $x = c - d^*$;

$$d^* \left(2 - \frac{d^*}{c} \right) = (Sf)^4 / (\alpha K)^2 \quad (15)$$

Substitution of Eqs. (15) and (8b) into Eq. (9c) then yields

$$K_p = (4/3\sqrt{\pi}) (Sf)^3 / \alpha K \quad (16)$$

In this case, the closure effect of the fibers for given K is manifest as a constant decrease in stress intensity factor (independent of crack length), so that the effect of the fibers is to increase the fracture toughness by $\Delta K_c = K_p$.

Strength/crack-size relations pertinent to this crack configuration can be conveniently compared with the results for the case where fibers do not fail behind the crack tip by normalizing the stresses and crack lengths with the parameters σ_m and c_m defined in the previous section. The relative toughness increase becomes

$$\Delta K_c / K_c = 2(Sf/\sigma_m)^3 \quad (17)$$

and the strength/crack-size relation becomes (Eqs. (9) and (16))

$$(\sigma/\sigma_m) = [1 + 2(Sf/\sigma_m)^3] / 3(c/c_m)^{1/2} \quad (18)$$

Equation (18) is plotted in Figure 3 for several values of the parameter Sf/σ_m . The result from Sect. 2.3 for multiple matrix cracking is also shown (curve labeled $Sf/\sigma_m > 1$). It is noted that, in these normalized coordinates, the crack response is determined by the parameter Sf/σ_m , i.e., the relative magnitudes of the fiber strength and the steady-state matrix cracking stress.

The curves in Figure 3 may be used to define transitions in the failure mechanism, as well as strength/crack-size relations. For $Sf/\sigma_m > 1$, the stress in the fibers does not exceed the fiber strength before multiple matrix cracking occurs. For $Sf/\sigma_m \leq 1$, the curves in Figure 3 represent lower bound strengths because the crack configuration at criticality depends on both the size of the pre-existing matrix crack and the initial fiber bridging state associated with the crack. Matrix cracks that occur in conjunction with failed fibers extend stably prior to failure with increasing

Figure 3 - Strength/crack-size relations for cracks fully bridged by fibers ($Sf/\sigma_m > 1$) and cracks with fiber failure occurring behind the crack tip ($Sf/\sigma_m < 1$).

fiber-bridging zone, d . This response can be characterized by an R-curve, as discussed in the following section. For large initial cracks, stable extension continues until fiber failure occurs (at $d = d^*$) and the strength of the composite is given by Eq. (18). However, for small cracks, instability precedes fiber failure, and the strength exceeds that given by Eq. (18). Matrix cracks that are initially fully bridged by fibers show three regions of behavior. For small cracks (i.e. $c < d^*$) the crack opening is insufficient to cause fiber failure at instability and the strength of the composite is given by Eq. (12). For intermediate sized cracks, the crack opening exceeds that required for fiber failure so that the bridging zone at criticality is defined by Eq. (15) and the strength is given by Eq. (18). The crack lengths at which this fiber-failure transition first occurs are given by the intersections of the curves in Figure 3 as expressed by setting $c = d^*$ in Eq. (15);

$$c/c_m = (Sf/\sigma_m)^4. \quad (19)$$

An upper limit on the range of crack lengths for which this failure mode pertains is imposed by the requirement that the applied stress exceeds the fiber strength for a fully bridged crack. Thus, at large crack lengths, where Sf exceeds the strength defined by Eq. (18), the applied load must be increased to Sf to cause fiber failure (whereupon, failure of the composite occurs catastrophically).

Discussion

Crack Growth Resistance

Failure from matrix cracks that have an initial bridging zone $d > d^*$ is characterized by a well-defined fracture toughness for ($Sf < \sigma_m$). However, cracks with a bridging zone smaller than d^* extend stably before fracture. In this case, a unique fracture toughness cannot be defined. Instead, the prefailure growth is characterized by crack-growth-resistance curves. These curves can be evaluated by defining an initial unbridged crack of length $c = c_o$, and allowing the crack to extend so that a fiber bridging zone (of length d) develops and the total crack length becomes $c = c_o + d$. Then the R-curve, defined by Eq. (9) with $K_R = K_\infty$ at $K = K_c$, can be expressed in the normalized form

$$K_R/K_c = 1 + 2 (d/c_m)^{3/4} [2 - (d/c_m)(c_o/c_m + d/c_m)^{-1}]^{3/4} \quad (20)$$

The R-curves for various values of c_o/c_m are plotted in Fig. 4. Also plotted are the limiting toughnesses, obtained from Eq. (17), for several values of Sf/σ_m . The intersections of these two sets of curves define the critical bridging zone size d^* , for each value of c_o/c_m and Sf/σ_m .

The condition for failure (i.e., unstable crack growth) is defined by $K_\infty = K_R$ and $dK_\infty/dc = dK_R/dc$. Thus, the crack stability depends on the slope of the R-curve, which in turn is dictated by the initial unbridged crack length, c_o . For large cracks, stable growth occurs until $d = d^*$ and K_R equals the limiting toughness. For smaller initial cracks, instability may be achieved at $d < d^*$. Fully bridged matrix cracks exhibit instability without precursor stable growth.

Figure 4 - Crack growth resistance curves for cracks with broken fibers over a radius c_o .

Size of the Fiber-Bridging Zone

The critical bridging zone size is defined by Eq. (15). The solution, at $K = K_C$, can be expressed in the normalized form

$$(d^*/c_m') = (c/c_m')[1 - (1 - c_m'/c)^{1/2}] \quad (21)$$

where $c_m' = c_m(Sf/\sigma_m)^4$. The plot of Eq. (21) in Figure 5 reveals that the size of the bridging zone in the large-crack-length limit is smaller by a factor of two than the crack length at which fiber failure first occurs. Moreover, the limiting zone size is first approached for cracks larger by about a factor of three than the crack that first experiences fiber failure.

Influence of Microstructural Parameters

The use of normalized strengths and crack lengths has enabled the mechanics and mechanisms of crack growth to be examined in the previous sections independently of the specific material and microstructural properties. The role of these microstructural properties can be readily evaluated through their influence on the normalizing parameters (Eqs. (8) and (13));

Figure 5 - Variation of critical zone size, d^* , with crack length.

$$\sigma_m = [12(1 - \nu^2)K_o \tau E_f f^2 (1 - f)(1 + \eta)^2 / E_m R]^{1/3} \quad (22)$$

$$c_m = [(9\pi^{3/2}/32) K_o E_m (1 - f)^2 (1 + \eta) R / \tau f^2 E_f (1 - \nu^2)]^{2/3} \quad (23)$$

In a previous study, predictions of σ_m in several composites that exhibit multiple matrix cracking were shown to be in accord with experimental observations. For the failure mechanism that involves simultaneous fiber failure and matrix cracking, the limiting fracture toughness increase is

$$\Delta K_c = S^3 f E_m R / 6 E_f \tau K_o (1 + \eta) \quad (24)$$

and the range of crack lengths for which the limiting toughness applies (i.e., $c > d^*$) is defined by Eq. (21)

$$c > (\pi/8) [S^2 E_m R / (1 - \nu^2) K_o \tau E_f (1 + \eta)]^2 \quad (25)$$

It is interesting to note that the influences of all material parameters on ΔK_c are opposite to their influence on the stress for steady-state multiple matrix cracking (i.e., σ_m).

Conclusions

The present fracture mechanics analysis of matrix cracking in uniaxial, brittle-fiber/brittle-matrix composites has allowed evaluation of crack growth behavior for two distinct mechanisms of failure. It has also enabled failure conditions and transitions between the two failure mechanisms to be related to microstructural properties of the composite.

It is acknowledged that the approximate crack profile used to obtain analytical solutions introduces some uncertainty. However, comparison with an exact numerical solution for the multiple cracking mechanism has shown that this uncertainty is not large. More importantly, the general trends predicted by the analysis are expected to apply and the roles of microstructural parameters, which enter through the normalizing parameters c_m and σ_m , are not affected by the approximation, since exact numerical solutions can be plotted in the same normalized coordinates.

References

1. A.G. Evans, M.D. Thouless, D.B. Johnson-Walls, E. Luh, and D.B. Marshall, "Some Structural Properties of Ceramic Matrix Fiber Composites," this volume.
2. J.J. Brennan and K.M. Prewo, "Silicon Carbide Fiber Reinforced Glass-Ceramic Matrix Composites Exhibiting High Strength and Toughness," J. Mater. Sci. 17[8] (1982) pp. 2371-83.
3. J. Aveston, G.A. Cooper, and A. Kelly, "Single and Multiple Fracture," pp. 15-26 in the Properties of Fiber Composites, Conf. Proc. Nat. Physical Lab., IPC Science and Technology Pres Ltd., Surrey, England, 1971.
4. D.B. Marshall and A.G. Evans, "Failure Mechanisms in Ceramic-Fiber/Ceramic-Matrix Composites," J. Amer. Ceram. Soc., in press.
5. R.A.J. Sambell, A. Briggs, D.C. Phillips, and D.H. Bowen, "Carbon Fiber Composites with Ceramic and Glass Matrices, Part 2 - Continuous Fibers," J. Mater. Sci. 7[6],(1972) pp. 676-681.
6. D.C. Phillips, "Interfacial Bonding and the Toughness of Carbon Fiber Reinforced Glass and Glass-Ceramics," J. Mater. Sci. 9[11], (1974) pp. 1847-54.
7. D.B. Marshall and A.G. Evans, "The Mechanics of Matrix Cracking in Brittle-Matrix Fiber Composites," Acta. Met., in press.